

Brand Preference of Cosmetics Products among College Boys in Ramanathapuram District, Tamilnadu

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Abstract

The Consumer Products Preference plays an important role of marketing. The study influenced by various factors of cosmetics products. In the changing global scenario to identify the consumer's needs and wants to buy a product. In this study titled “Brand Preference of Cosmetic products among College Boys in Ramanathapuram Districts”. A sample of 200 boys' students was selected on the basis of stratified random sampling method. The statistical tools used for analysis, such as percentage, Garrett's ranking and Likert's five point scale from this study. It was formal that the majority of the college boys are preferred Hamam Soap, Ponds Sandal talcum Powder, Clinic-plus Shampoo and V.V.D. Coconut Hair oil and Eva body spray.

Keywords: Brand Preference, Brand, Consumer, Cosmetics, Loyalty, Price Sensitivity.

Introduction

The first archaeological evidence of cosmetics usage was found in Ancient Egypt around 4000BC. The Ancient Greeks and Romans also used cosmetics. In the Western World, cosmetics were used throughout the medieval period, although their use was typically restricted to the upper classes. The popularity of cosmetics in the 20th century has increased rapidly. Especially in the USA cosmetics are being used by teens at a younger and younger age, many companies have catered to this expanding market by introducing more flavored lipsticks and glosses. Cosmetics packaged in glittery, sparkly packaging and marketing and advertising using young girls and boys. Cosmetics are substances prepared to improve beautify and generally increase the attractiveness of a person. As cosmetic products consists of numerous items only five products, namely bathing soap, face powder, shampoo, hair-oil and body spray have been selected for this study.

Review of Literature

C.Muthuvelayutham (2012) in his study titled “The study of Consumer Brand loyalty on FMCG-Cosmetic Products with Referred to Madurai” analyze the relationship among demographic variables with the brand loyalty of the consumers and tries to identify the

consumers switching factors in the selected product category. A random sample of 600 from South Tamilnadu namely Madurai, Tuticorin, Kanyakumari districts were selected for analysis. The chi - square test was used in this study. Results show that among the variables, age, literacy level and gender have the most significant impact on consumer brand loyalty.

Dr.S.Mahalingam, P.Nandhakumar (2012) “A study on consumer behavior towards selected FMCGs in Coimbatore City” focuses their efforts on analysis the socio-economic profile of the sample respondents and their shopping pattern and assesses the factors influencing the consumer to purchase the selected FMCG products. This research used statistical tools in percentage analysis and Garrett the author concludes that quality is the motivating factor for the consumer to buy the product of FMCG.

P.Devibala, Dr.A.Rengaswamy (2011) in his article “Consumer Preference for Cosmetics among College Girls in Tirunelveli and Thoothukudi Districts”. The primary data was collected through a questionnaire. It focuses their consumer preference for cosmetics among college girls and whether the college girls are satisfied with the brand available, analysis and understand whether they are satisfied with the present price of cosmetics and was conducted on a sample of 150 college girls.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objective of the study,

1. To study the consumer brand preference for cosmetics among college boys with reference to Ramanathapuram district.
2. To analysis the popular brand of cosmetics used by majority of college boys with reference to Ramanathapuram district.
3. To find out whether the college boys are satisfied with the brands available at present.
4. To offer suggestions so as to meet the solution of problems faced by the respondents.

Area of the Study

“This study has been undertaken in four colleges, covering Ramanathapuram district such as Sethupathy Government Arts College Ramanathapuram, Syed Ammal Arts and science college, Ramanathapuram, seasonal college of Arts and Science, Muthupettai, Syed Hameetha college of Arts and science college, keelakarai Ramanathapuram district.

Scope of the Study

This study confined to brand preference of cosmetic products among the boy students in selected four colleges from the Ramanathapuram district only.

Period of the Study

The study has been undertaken during a period of six months from August 2017 to December 2017.

Source of Data

The study has been collected both from primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected from sample respondents with the help of an interview schedule. The secondary data have been collected from books, magazines and journals website and the like.

Sampling Design

A sample of 200 college boys from selected colleges have been chosen as respondents on the basis of stratified random sampling method. The details of sample are depicted in Table 1.

Tools Used for Analysis

Such as averages, percentage, weighted average, mean, Garret’s ranking technique have been used for analysis and interpretation of the data collected.

Table 1 Respondents College Wise

S.No.	District	Name of the College	Arts	Science	Total
1	Sivagangai	1.. Sethupathy Government Arts College Ramanathapuram	22	28	50
		2. Syed Ammal Arts and science college, Ramanathapuram,	30	20	50
		3. caussanel college of Arts and Science, Muthupettai	18	32	50
			30	20	50
Total			100	100	200

1. Percentage

$$\frac{\text{No. of Respondents}}{\text{Total No. of Respondents}} \times 100$$

2. Garrett Score Method

$$\text{Percentage Position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where R_{ij} = Ranking given for ith factor by the jth respondents
 N_j = Number of various ranked by the jth respondents

3. Weighted Average

$$= \frac{\text{Row Total}}{\text{No. of Respondents}}$$

Items of Cosmetics

The five items of cosmetics that are normally used by college boys have been selected for the study. They are (1) Bathing Soap (2) Face Powder (3) Shampoo (4) Hair oil (5) Body Spray

Table 2 Age of the Respondent

S.No.	Age Group	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Up to 20	110	55
2	20 – 22	62	31
3	Above 23	28	14
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary data

Table 2 shows that out of 200 respondents 110 are below 20 years and remaining 62 are between the age of 20 and 23.

Expenditure of Cosmetics

Table 3 shows the details of the expenditure incurred by the respondents per month.

Table 3 Expenditure of Cosmetics (pm)

S.No.	Income (Rs.)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Below 250	66	33
2	250 – 500	104	52
3	Above 500	30	15
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 indicates that out of 200 sample respondents 52 percent of the respondents spend Rs.250 – Rs.500 per month, 33 per cent of respondents spend up to Rs.250 and only a 15 per cent of the respondents spend above Rs. 500 per month for cosmetics.

Preference of Cosmetics

The preferences for different cosmetics of the respondents have been analyzed one after another. Table 4 shows the preference for bathing soap.

Table 4 Preference of Bothing Soap of the Sample Respondents

S.No.	Options	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Hamam	51	26
2	Cinthol	33	16
3	Lux	38	19
4	Mysore Sandal	22	11
5	Lifebuoy	27	13
6	Rexsona	12	06
7	Pears	10	05
8	Other Soaps	07	04
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary data

Table 4 shows that about 51 respondents covering 26 per cent prefer Hamam Soap, Lux Soap and Cinthol Soaps ranked second and third in preference.

Table 5 Preferences for Talcum Powder

S.No.	Preference	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Ponds – Sandal	84	42
2	Gokul – Sandal	42	21
3	Cuticura	31	15
4	Spinz	24	12
5	Others	19	10
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary data

Table 5 shows that a majority of 42 per cent of the respondents preferred to use Ponds Sandal, next 21 per cent Gokul Sandal, followed by the Cuticura 15 per cent, Spinz has been preferred by 12 per cent.

Preference of Shampoo

The analysis shows that a majority of 33 per cent of the respondents preferred to use Clinic Plus Shampoo, next is for Head and Shoulder 26 per cent, followed by check 13 per cent and Dove Shampoo has been preferred by only 5 per cent. These things have been displayed in Table 6.

Table 6 Preferences for Shampoo

S.No.	Preference	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Clinic Plus	66	33
2	Sun Silk	24	12
3	Head and Shoulder	52	26
4	Chik	26	13
5	Pantene	22	11
6	Dove	10	05
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary data

Preference of Hair oil

Table 7 Preference of Hair Oil of the Sample Respondents

S.No.	Preference	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Parachute	46	23
2	V.V.D. Coconut oil	58	29
3	Dabur Amla	32	16
4	Aswini	30	15
5	Vatika	24	12
6	Navaratna	10	05
	Total	200	100

Source: Primary data

Table 7 shows that about 58 respondents covered 29 per cent preferred V.V.D. Coconut oil followed by Parachute 23 per cent, 16 per cent Dabur Amla, Vatika 12 per cent and finally Navaratna 5 per cent.

Factors Influencing Brand Preference

The students expressed the following factors that have influenced them to prefer a particular item of cosmetics. The factors have been depicted in Table 8, Garrets Ranking Techniques has been used to analysis the factors influencing the preference for the selection of brands of cosmetic products by the college boys, the percentage position is calculated by using the following formula:
 Percentage Position = $100 (R_{ij} - 05) / N_j$

Table 8 Factors Influencing Brand Preference

S. No.	Factor	Rank								Total No. of Respondents	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
1	Quality	53	38	31	26	22	8	14	8	200	11986	59.93	I
2	Reasonable Price	40	12	18	32	28	23	25	22	200	10256	51.28	IV
3	Brand image	12	22	32	43	27	30	23	11	200	10058	50.29	V
4	Package	11	20	21	38	32	37	20	21	200	9538	47.69	VIII
5	Fragrance	41	32	23	28	19	20	25	12	200	11021	55.10	III
6	Freshness	23	12	20	38	32	37	18	20	200	9818	49.09	VII
7	Advertisement	16	22	29	32	22	28	38	13	200	9820	49.1	VI
8	Health Care	44	36	39	30	16	20	10	05	200	11834	59.17	II
	Garrettes Table value	80	67	60	53	47	40	32	20				

Table 8 shows the number of respondents ranking the factors at 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 for the brand preference of cosmetics products; it also shows the total score and the mean score. Table 8 shows that according to the Garrett ranking the factors which induces the respondents to show preference for the brands of cosmetics products among college boys are in this order, namely Quality, Health Care, Fragrance, Reasonable Price, Brand image, Advertisement, Freshness and Package.

For Factor quality the total score is calculated by multiplying the number of respondents ranking that factor as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 by their respective table values given in Table 8. Mean score is calculated by dividing the total score by the number of respondents. The respondents were asked to rank the eight factors identified for the purpose of this study as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 in order to know their preferences in the selection of brands of cosmetic products, the calculate percentage positions for the ranks 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 and their corresponding Garrett’s Table values are given in Table 9.

Table 9 Percentage Position and their Corresponding Garretts Table Values

Rank	Percentage Position	Calculate Value	Garrett’s Table Value
	$100 (R_{ij} - 0.5) / N_{ij}$		
1	$100 (1-0.5) / 8$	6.25	80
2	$100 (2-0.5) / 8$	18.75	67
3	$100 (3-0.5) / 8$	31.25	60
4	$100 (4-0.5) / 8$	43.75	53
5	$100 (5-0.5) / 8$	56.25	47
6	$100 (6-0.5) / 8$	68.75	40
7	$100 (7-0.5) / 8$	81.25	32
8	$100 (8-0.5) / 8$	93.75	20

Table 9 shows that the percentage positions in the ranks 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8 their corresponding Garrets table value. For Rank 1 is calculated position is 6.25 and Garretts table value is 80. Table value is 80. This value is given in the Garrets ranking table for the percentage 6.14 which is very near 6. As like of all the calculated percentage positions the table value is referred from Garrets ranking table.

Satisfaction Level

The satisfaction level of the respondents has been measured by the likes five point scale, such as (Highly Satisfied (HS), Satisfied (SA), Neutral (N), Dissatisfied (DS) and Highly Dissatisfied (HDS). Table 11 shows that the overall satisfaction is hair-oil, Bathing Soap and Talcum Powder while applying like table scale of finding out the rank of level of Satisfaction the following weight are allotted (HS: 5, S: 4, N: 3, DS: 2 and HDS: 1)

Table 10 Over All Satisfaction Level of Cosmetics Products

S.No	Cosmetics	HS	SAT	N	DS	HDS	Row Total	Weight Average	Rank
1	Bathing Soap	330 (66)	208 (52)	120 (40)	52 (26)	16 (16)	726	3.63	II
2	Talcum Powder	315 (63)	200 (50)	132 (44)	48 (24)	19 (19)	714	3.57	III
3	Shampoo	300 (60)	204 (51)	96 (32)	60 (30)	27 (27)	687	3.43	IV
4	Hair Oil	425 (85)	168 (42)	105 (35)	40 (20)	18 (18)	756	3.78	I

Source: Primary data

Findings of the Study

The following are the main findings of the study

1. Majority of the respondents are spending Rs.200 to Rs.500 per month on cosmetics.
2. Majority the college boys are use of cosmetics age of the respondents under 20 years.
3. Hamam is the most preferred bathing soap by a majority of the respondents.
4. Ponds Sandal is most preferred Talcum Powder by more than average number of respondents.
5. Clinic plus Shampoo are the preferred number of respondents.
6. V.V.D. Coconut oil and Parachute Oil are preferred more equally by the average number of respondents.
7. The overall satisfaction is hair-oil, bathing soap and followed by talcum Powder.

Suggestions

1. The respondents feel that the prices of cosmetics are comparatively higher. Hence it is suggested that manufacturer should concentrate on product changes and diversification in the cosmetics, through which they can reduce the prices.
2. Label information accurately as consumer would like it if simplified.
3. The cosmetic product company must focus on television advertisement keeping the rural markets in mind.
4. FMCG companies should create awareness about the usage of shampoo and hair oil, educate the product value and increase their market share.
5. The rural respondent's usage of shampoo, hair oil and talcum powder is very meager. It shows that they follow traditional methods and need for more awareness about the product usage and its benefits.

Conclusion

It is concluded from this study that cosmetic sector is growing and will continue to grow very fast. In India the market share of cosmetic industry contributes a considerable amount of FMCG sector, which is continuously increasing from year to year. Quality is the main motivating factor for the consumer to buy the product of cosmetic. From this analysis, it is inferred that the respondents given greater importance to the factors of quality and health care with compared to factors in the selection of cosmetic product.

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